

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Development of mangosteen marketing strategies in the “Langgeng Ari Guna” (LAG) Group

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2025, 25(03), 1741-1748

Publication history: Received on 08 February 2025; revised on 16 March 2025; accepted on 19 March 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2025.25.3.0856>

Abstract

The research design used is descriptive qualitative where data is obtained through interviews, documentation, and literature study methods. This study used a questionnaire as a data collection instrument. The research location is in the Langgeng Ari Guna Group, Mundeh Kangin Village, West Selemadeg District, Tabanan Regency. Primary data were obtained through the distribution of research questionnaires. Secondary data were obtained through literature studies in accordance with the research topic. The results of data analysis show that (1) the total strength score is 1.96 while the total weakness score is 0.80. So that the total score in the Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE) analysis is 2.76. (2) the total opportunity score is 1.96 while the total threat score is 0.66. So that the total score in the External Factor Evaluation is 2.62. (3) Based on SWOT analysis (Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threat), the Langgeng Ari Guna Group is in quadrant I, which means it is suitable to implement an aggressive strategy. Alternative strategies obtained from matching internal and external factors in quadrant I (S-O) are (a) Increasing the competence of group members related to mangosteen agribusiness as well as to support the development of Mundeh Kangin tourist village (S6, S7, S8, O4, O5, O6, O7). (b) Improve the quality and quantity of mangosteen production in the Langgeng Ari Guna Group (S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, O1, O2, O3). (4) Referring to the results of the QSPM (Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix) analysis, it was found that the alternative strategy that has the highest TAS (Total Attractiveness Score) value (6.41) is to increase the competence of group members related to mangosteen agribusiness as well as to support the development of the Mundeh Kangin tourist village. This prioritized alternative strategy in its implementation can be supported by an appropriate action plan.

Keywords: Marketing strategy; IFE analysis; EFE analysis; SWOT analysis; QSPM

1. Introduction

Mangosteen is a potential commodity to be developed in Tabanan Regency. This condition is also supported by the 2020-2024 horticultural development policy which essentially encourages increased production, market access, exports supported by sustainable environmentally friendly cultivation and encourages increased added value of commodities to improve the welfare of farmers (Anonymous, 2022a). Mangosteen is a tropical fruit that has a unique taste and aroma, delicious, and fresh where this fruit is found in Southeast Asia. Medically, mangosteen also has a myriad of health benefits that are useful for the body both from the pulp and the skin of the mangosteen fruit itself. This reason makes mangosteen fruit the target and favorite of consumers both in the domestic and export markets. According to data from the Central Bureau of Statistics of Bali Province (2022), mangosteen fruit production in Tabanan Regency in 2022 was 47,399 quintals from 19,992 trees (TM). Upstream and downstream aspects of mangosteen cultivation must be improved to produce mangosteen fruit with good quantity and quality. This is important for the sustainability of this farming business both in the short and long term.

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The Langgeng Ari Guna Group, Mundeh Kangin Village, West Selemadeg District, Tabanan Regency, Bali Province is one of the groups active in marketing mangosteen in Tabanan Regency. Although it is a new group, it has shown its seriousness and dedication to the development of mangosteen farming in Tabanan Regency. The group, which was inaugurated in 2022, consists of 24 mangosteen farmers. So far, the Langgeng Ari Guna Group has received various forms of training and coaching from relevant agencies in order to increase the competence and capacity of group members both in terms of upstream and downstream mangosteen commodities. The training, coaching and facilitation include 1) application of integrated pest control (PPHT) of mangosteen commodities, 2) application of SL-GAP (Field School of good agriculture practices), 3) Technical guidance on the application of GHP (good handling practices), 4) farm registration, and 5) Prima 3 certification. Furthermore, the Langgeng Ari Guna Group, Mundeh Kangin Village, West Selemadeg District, Tabanan Regency, Bali Province has expanded its marketing reach by cooperating through an MOU (Memorandum of Understanding) with PT Manggis Elok Utama related to mangosteen fruit marketing for the export market and post-harvest assistance.

However, despite having great potential to capture the domestic and export markets, mangosteen marketing in the Langgeng Ari Guna Group, Mundeh Kangin Village, West Selemadeg District, Tabanan Regency, Bali Province is also not free from various challenges and risks. Referring to the opinion of Ngatno (2018), marketing is an activity that is interconnected and related as a system to generate profits. Often the problems faced by a business are caused by disharmonious relationships between the parties in marketing itself because of making inappropriate marketing policies or strategies.

2. Literature Review

Marketing actually includes all activities carried out from the feather side to the downstream of an agricultural commodity. Marketing aims to meet consumer demand in a timely manner, right amount, right place, right quality and right price. This is what encourages producers (farmers) to compete to produce agricultural products that have competitiveness in the market. Basically, the competitiveness of agricultural commodities is closely related to the extent to which these commodities are able to meet market preferences. This condition will be met if agricultural commodity marketing policies are based on internal and external factors owned by each agribusiness institution.

The development of marketing strategies is an interesting solution that has strategic value in order to produce good alternative strategies. The Langgeng Ari Guna group is one of the agribusiness institutions that needs support through a study of mangosteen marketing strategy development. So far, there has never been a comprehensive strategy development study conducted on the Langgeng Ari Guna Group. Ideally, studies related to the development of marketing strategies are needed to face the dynamic market dynamics. This is a preventive effort in order to avoid this group from the marketing risks that always loom.

3. Methods

This study used a descriptive qualitative research design, where data were obtained using in-depth interviews, documentation, and literature studies. The research was conducted at the Langgeng Ari Guna Group, Mundeh Kangin Village, West Selemadeg District, Tabanan Regency from October to December 2024. Primary data was obtained through interviews and distributing questionnaires to 24 members of the Langgeng Ari Guna Group for the needs of assessing internal and external factors. The assessment of alternative strategies prioritized using three key informants consisting of representatives of the Tabanan Regency Agriculture Office, Academics and the Head of the Langgeng Ari Guna Group (practitioners). The analytical tools used are IFE, EFE, SWOT and QSPM

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Internal Factor Evaluation Analysis (IFE)

The identification of internal factors in the object under study is the first step in the formulation of marketing strategies that can later be offered to interested parties. In this study, the identification of these factors was carried out at the Langgeng Ari Guna Group located in Mundeh Kangin Village, West Selemadeg District, Tabanan Regency. Identification was carried out by conducting in-depth discussions with the Langgeng Ari Guna Group. The research respondents then rated each detail of the internal factors of the Langgeng Ari Guna Group for further analysis to obtain data related to the score of each internal factor. The results of the identification of these internal factors will be an input for the formulation of alternative strategies for the Langgeng Ari Guna Group.

Table 1 Internal Factor Evaluation Analysis (IFE)

Code	Internal Factor	Score	Rate	Total
		a	b	(axb)
S1	Mangosteen is a horticultural commodity that is in demand by consumers	0.08	4	0.32
S2	Mangosteen as a horticultural commodity that has a clear market	0.06	3	0.19
S3	Mangosteen is a leading export commodity	0.08	4	0.32
S4	Ease of access to production inputs (seeds, fertilizers, medicines)	0.06	3	0.17
S5	Agro-climatic and soil conditions that are suitable for mangosteen plants	0.08	3	0.24
S6	Characteristics of agrarian communities that have long experience in farming	0.08	3	0.24
S7	Training and coaching support from government, private and academic elements (universities)	0.06	3	0.19
S8	Mangosteen is designated as the icon of Mundeh Kangin Village	0.07	4	0.29
		0.58	27	1.96
W1	Promotion of mangosteen commodities has not been maximized	0.06	3	0.19
W2	The decline in the price of mangosteen fruit during the harvest season	0.06	1	0.06
W3	The location of the plantation is far away the productivity of production is still not optimal	0.05	2	0.10
W4	Farmers' knowledge related to good on farm and off farm on mangosteen commodities is not maximized	0.06	2	0.13
W5	The grade of mangosteen fruit in the export market produced by farmers is still influenced by mangosteen produced by Thailand and the Philippines	0.06	2	0.13
W6	Product quality is still not optimal	0.06	1	0.06
W7	Promotion of mangosteen commodities has not been maximized	0.06	2	0.13
		0.42	13	0.80
		1.00	40	2.76
	Difference (X)			1.16

Primary Data, 2024

Based on the results of the data calculation as presented above, it is known that the total score of the internal factors of the Langgeng Ari Guna Group is 2.76. This indicates that the Langgeng Ari Guna Group has relatively strong internal factors where the internal factor score is greater than 2.5. The strengths owned by the Langgeng Ari Guna Group appear to dominate the weaknesses of the group. The internal factor score is influenced by the strength score of 1.96 and the weakness score of 0.80. The difference between the strength and weakness scores is 1.16. This fact confirms that this group is quite progressive in carrying out internal development even though it is still a newly formed group. The dominance of the strength score over weaknesses in the Langgeng Ari Guna Group can be understood as a form of the group's ability to utilize all of its potential strengths. The Langgeng Ari Guna Group has the potential to move forward to face various forms of competition by optimizing strengths and minimizing the impact of its weaknesses.

4.2. External Factor Evaluation Analysis (EFE)

Identification of external factors on the object under study is the first step in formulating a marketing strategy that can later be offered to interested parties. In this study, the identification of these factors was carried out at the Langgeng Ari Guna Group located in Mundeh Kangin Village, West Selemadeg District, Tabanan Regency. Identification was carried out by conducting in-depth discussions with the Langgeng Ari Guna Group. The research respondents then rated each detail of the external factors of the Langgeng Ari Guna Group for further analysis so that data related to the score of each external factor was obtained. The results of the identification of these external factors will be an input for the formulation of alternative strategies for the Langgeng Ari Guna Group.

Table 2 External Factor Evaluation Analysis (EFE)

Code	External Factor	Score	Rate	Total
		a	b	(axb)
O1	Mangosteen commodities have great opportunities both in the domestic and export markets	0.09	4	0.36
O2	Development of cultivation and post-harvest technology of mangosteen commodities	0.09	3	0.27
O3	Mutually beneficial partnership relationships between farmer groups and exporting companies	0.08	4	0.33
O4	Mundeh Kangin Tourism Village development policy	0.07	3	0.20
O5	Healthy lifestyle trends in society	0.09	4	0.36
O6	Mangosteen commodities are ingredients for equipment for Hindu religious ceremonies Hindu religious ceremonies in Bali	0.08	4	0.30
O7	Development of derivative products made from mangosteen commodities	0.05	3	0.14
		0.54	25	1.96
T1	The threat of middlemen to the selling price of mangosteen commodities	0.09	1	0.09
T2	Decrease in people's purchasing power	0.09	1	0.09
T3	Pest and plant disease attacks	0.07	2	0.14
T4	Changes in prerequisites requested by importing countries	0.07	2	0.14
T5	Weather anomalies that have an impact on reducing the quality and quantity of production	0.07	2	0.14
T6	Weak bargaining power of farmers in the market	0.08	1	0.08
		0.46	9	0.66
		1	34	2.62
	Differences (Y)			1.30

Primary Data, 2024

Based on the data presented in table 2 above, it is known that the total score for opportunities (opportunity) is 1.96 while the total score for threats (treath) is 0.66. The difference between the opportunity and threat scores is 1.30. Basically, the opportunities owned by the Langgeng Ari Guna Group are greater than the threats, however, seeing the difference in scores that are not too far adrift requires strategic steps so that existing opportunities can be utilized while minimizing the potential threats that exist.

The total score of the external factor evaluation (EFE) of the Langgeng Ari Guna Group is 2.62, which means relatively opportunity. This condition is an advantage that must be captured by the group in its future marketing development. The group's ability to take advantage of opportunities and avoid threats in mangosteen marketing can be done in various ways including (1) education and training, (2) improving analytical skills and strategic decision making, (3) increasing communication and collaboration with all stakeholders, (4) adjusting capital support to the needs of the group, (5) introducing the latest technology to increase efficiency and effectiveness.

4.3. Formulation of Alternative Strategies

Rangkuti (2006) states that SWOT (Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threat) analysis is a process of systematically identifying relevant factors in the formulation of business strategies. Through the use of SWOT analysis (Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threat) the company can design a strategy that allows it to take advantage of its strengths, suppress weaknesses, increase while capturing existing opportunities and reduce the risk of threats to the company's business continuity (Kolbina, 2015 in Suryani 2017). SWOT analysis (Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threat) can help the Langgeng Ari Guna Group in formulating alternative strategies in mangosteen marketing.

Mangosteen marketing strategy in the Langgeng Ari Guna Group can be known from the preparation of the SWOT analysis diagram (Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threat). The formulation of marketing strategies using SWOT analysis (Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threat) is based on the results of identification and analysis of internal and external factors. The SWOT (Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threat) analysis diagram is a Cartesian diagram consisting of four quadrants. Quadrant I support aggressive strategies, quadrant II supports diversification strategies, quadrant III supports defensive strategies and quadrant IV supports turn around strategies. Analysis results. Figure 1 below presents the SWOT analysis diagram of the Langgeng Ari Guna Group.

Figure 1 SWOT Grand Strategy Matrix Source

Based on the diagram in Figure 1 above, it is known that the X-axis value is 1.16 while the Y-axis value is 1.30. This means that the Langgeng Ari Guna Group is in quadrant I which supports an aggressive growth policy (Growth). Mashuri and Nurjannah (2020) stated that a growth strategy is important to generate growth in various ways including price adjustments, developing new products, improving product and service quality, and opening wider access to the market. Referring to the position of the Langgeng Ari Guna Group which is in quadrant I, it is then continued by formulating a strategy whose essence is to maximize the strengths it has while capturing all existing opportunities (S-O).

The next step is to formulate an alternative strategy by combining internal and external factors owned by the Langgeng Ari Guna Group. Matching is done by following the following formula (1) strength-opportunity (S-O), (2) weakness-opportunity (W-O), (3) strength-threat (S-T), (4) weakness-threat (W-T).

4.4. Prioritized Alternative Strategies

Determination of prioritized alternative strategies is done using the QSPM (Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix) analysis tool. Based on the SWOT (Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threat) analysis conducted, it is known that the Langgeng Ari Guna Group is in quadrant I (S-O). The alternative strategies obtained from combining the strength-opportunity (S-O) elements are three alternative strategies. The alternative strategies are as follows:

- Increasing the competence of group members related to mangosteen agribusiness while also supporting the development of the Mundeh Kangin tourist village (S6, S7, S8, O4, O5, O6, O7).
- Improving the quality and quantity of mangosteen production in the Langgeng Ari Guna Group (S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, O1, O2, O3).

The alternative strategies as mentioned above are then used as the main input in the QSPM (Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix) analysis in determining the prioritized alternative strategies.

4.5. Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix Analysis (QSPM)

The Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM) can help in determining the prioritized alternative strategies. Determining the priority of alternative strategies is important for at least several reasons, including resource efficiency, increasing focus and coordination in decision making, and reducing the risk of not achieving goals. Handayani and Sarwono (2021) emphasized that the Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM) method is an analysis method that is objectively able to determine the prioritized alternative strategies. This makes this method widely chosen by decision makers in various organizations.

The steps for formulating objectives, determining strategy options, and determining key success factors have been carried out in the previous analysis. Based on the results of the SWOT (Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threat) analysis, it is known that there are two alternative strategies that have been successfully formulated. QSPM (Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix) analysis to select one of the prioritized alternative strategies. QSPM (Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix) analysis is carried out by calculating the TAS (Total Attractiveness Score) value of each alternative strategy. TAS (Total Attractiveness Score) is the multiplication of the weight of each factor with the AS (Attractiveness Score) given by key informants. The alternative strategy with the highest TAS (Total Attractiveness Score) is the prioritized (selected) alternative strategy. Based on the results of the QSPM (Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix) analysis, it is known that the alternative strategy that has the highest Total Attractiveness Score (6.41) is to improve the competence of group members related to mangosteen agribusiness as well as to support the development of the Mundeh Kangin tourism village. Referring to the results above, the alternative strategy in question was chosen as a prioritized alternative strategy to be recommended to the Langgeng Ari Guna Group.

4.6. Action Plan

An action plan is a plan that contains concrete steps in order to realize the objectives to be achieved. Action plans are useful in achieving goals effectively and efficiently, minimizing risks, facilitating monitoring and evaluation, and maintaining the focus of work on the agreed path. In relation to the alternative strategies prioritized in the QSPM (Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix) analysis, the action plan prepared is the operationalization of the selected alternative strategies. Table 3 below presents the proposed action plan referring to the selected alternative strategy.

Table 3 Action Plan

No	Strategy	Action Plan
1	Improving the competence of group members related to mangosteen agribusiness as well as to support the development of the Mundeh Kangin tourist village	Some things that can be done include: Developing a holistic agribusiness training program for group members by presenting experts and related practitioners; Collaborating with Mundeh Kangin Village in providing support in the form of financing subsidies for group members who participate in mangosteen agribusiness competency improvement training in order to support the development of tourism villages; Collaborating with universities related to the dissemination of technology and the latest research results that can be applied in the Langgeng Ari Guna Group.

Primary Data, 2024

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of the internal factor identification, it was found that the Langgeng Ari Guna Group has eight strength factors with a total score of 1.96 and seven weakness factors with a total score of 0.80. Thus, the total score of the Langgeng Ari Guna Group's Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE) is 2.76. The difference in total score between the strength and weakness factors is 1.16. Meanwhile, based on the results of the external factor identification, it was found that the Langgeng Ari Guna Group has seven opportunity factors with a total score of 1.96 and six threat factors with a total score of 0.66. The total score of the External Factor Evaluation (EFE) is 2.62. The difference between the total score of opportunities and threats is 1.30.

Based on the results of the SWOT analysis (Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threat), it was found that the Langgeng Ari Guna Group is in quadrant I, making it suitable for implementing an aggressive strategy. The formulation of alternative strategies refers to the position of quadrant I (S-O) which produces two combinations of alternative strategies, namely: Increasing the quality and quantity of mangosteen production in the Langgeng Ari Guna Group and

Increasing the competence of group members related to mangosteen agribusiness to support the development of the Mundeh Kangin tourism village.

Based on the results of the QSPM (Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix) analysis, the results obtained were that the alternative strategy with the highest TAS (Total Attractiveness Score) value was Increasing the competence of group members related to mangosteen agribusiness as well as to support the development of the Mundeh Kangin tourism village. The proposed action plan in the operationalization of this strategy is (1) Preparing a holistic agribusiness training program for group members by presenting experts and related practitioners, (2) Providing subsidies or fully financing group members who take part in training to improve mangosteen agribusiness competence in order to support the development of tourism villages, (3) Collaborating with universities related to the dissemination of technology and the latest research results that can be applied in the Langgeng Ari Guna Group.

Suggestions

Based on the results of the research, the alternative strategy that is prioritized to be recommended is to improve the competence of group members related to mangosteen agribusiness as well as to support the development of the Mundeh Kangin tourism village. Referring to this, facilitation is needed in the form of mentoring, training, assistance with infrastructure and programmed promotion so that the Langgeng Ari Guna Group can run the mangosteen agribusiness well to support the development of the tourism village. Monitoring and evaluation need to be carried out involving relevant stakeholders regarding the mangosteen agribusiness in the Langgeng Ari Guna Group periodically so that the farming business carried out is in accordance with the direction and objectives of the group.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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